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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The FLEXCoop project has gathered researchers, ICT and energy companies together with energy cooperatives actors in order to develop and demonstrate new demand-side flexibility (DSF) tools and related business models for energy cooperatives. FLEXCoop's aim has been to contribute to the democratisation of the energy system by providing citizens initiatives with the tools to take a more active role in the energy system and open new services enabling them to accelerate the decarbonisation of our energy system. FLEXCoop has been a unique forum to discuss the role of citizens in the new energy landscape open by new technologies and opportunities created by the Clean Energy Package. In this context, FLEXCoop policy and market recommendations address a broad range of issues.

They first address the role of citizen initiatives in the context of the Clean Energy Package and of the emergence of new actors: the “energy communities” (Section 2).

They highlight the complementary rules needed to unleash the potential of demand-side flexibility services across the energy value chain. This includes the whole set of services enabled by DSF: (collective) self-consumption, balancing reserves, congestion management and wholesale market valorisation towards balance responsible parties (Sections 3). It also includes making accessible existing flexible resources by facilitating their connection through communication standards (Section 4).

The third key challenge for addressed here concerns the introduction of “big data”-based services from several perspectives. It includes the need for clear rules to facilitate commercial activities (Section 5); the need to safeguard individual rights through enhanced data protection (Section 6) and enable citizens collectives to anticipate the consequences of these new digital services (Section 7).

Finally, these recommendations are concluded by some key initiatives which could further support research in demand-side flexibility area (Section 8).

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ABBREVIATIONS

aFRR	automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves
BRP	Balance responsible Party
CEC	Citizen Energy Community
DER	Distributed Energy resources
DSF	Demand-Side Flexibility
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EBPD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU ETS	European Union’s Emissions Trading Scheme
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IDSA	International data Spaces Association
IEMD	Internal Electricity Market Directive
ISP	Imbalance Settlement Period
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
PMV	Performance Measurement and Verification
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Community
REDII	Renewable Energy Directive (recast)
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAC	Security and Access Control
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SG-Ready	“Smart Grid Ready” label for heat pumps
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TSO	Transmission System Operator
USEF	Universal Smart Energy Framework

1. INTRODUCTION

The FLEXCoop project has gathered researchers, ICT and energy companies together with energy cooperatives actors in order to develop and demonstrate new demand-side flexibility tools and related business models for energy cooperatives. FLEXCoop's aim has been to contribute to the democratisation of the energy system by providing citizens initiatives with the tools to take a more active role in the energy system and open new services which enable them to accelerate the decarbonisation of our energy system.

This project has taken place in specific regulatory times, while the Clean Energy Package was being approved and implemented. The Clean Energy Package is a set of eight directives and regulations approved between 2018 and 2019 and aiming at revamping the Internal Energy Market. It is being a major shift in the EU energy sector for three reasons. First, it further deepens the Internal Electricity Market, streamlining national rules and providing more opportunities for trans-European business to thrive in the energy sector. Second, it accompanies EU commitments towards decarbonisation with a set of rules to further integrate Renewable Energy Sources (RES) into the EU energy mix, but also to integrate new actors and business models based on digital technology aimed at supporting a rapidly changing and more dynamic energy system. Finally, while the energy sector's liberalisation process was defining end-users' role as "consumer" or "customer", for the first time, the role of "citizens" initiatives is taking into account and valorised in the EU legislation.

In this context, the FLEXCoop project has been a unique forum representing diverse actors to discuss the role of citizens in the energy policy, the role of new technologies to enable the energy transition and the key role of data, including the need for privacy and but also new opportunities digital energy services may open to citizens initiatives. As a result, the policy and market recommendations below address different challenges from the role of citizen organisations (the new "energy communities") to the opportunity given for new digital services in the different electricity market. The question of data comes at a central place as it represents the raw material of these innovative energy services. This comes together with enhanced technical, commercial, but also democratic challenges around the management of fast-increasing energy data volumes. Finally, these critical times for the energy sector also command to provide space for research and innovation at all stages to address these challenges.

2. SUPPORTING ENERGY COMMUNITIES IN ADDRESSING THE WHOLE ENERGY SECTOR

Energy communities may support demand-side flexibility services, but not only. Though they should be encouraged to support the development of innovative services for RES integration, their role should not be limited to few specific activities. In the various fora where FLEXCoop has been involved, the concepts of renewable and citizen energy communities tended to be confused with collective self-consumption or energy trading. Whereas they have great potential when combined, these are different concepts.

2.1. Energy communities are not related to specific activities

The Internal Electricity Market Directive [1] (also known as Electricity Directive) defines the concept of Citizen Energy Community and the Renewable Energy Directive [2] defines Renewable Energy Communities. The existence of two definitions is mainly explained by the legal perimeter of each text:

- Citizen energy community belongs to the Electricity Directive. Therefore, it includes all activities related to electricity, but excludes gas, biomass and other sources of heat.
- Renewable Energy Community belongs to the Renewable Energy Directive. Therefore, it includes all activities related to renewables (incl. biomass, biogas, etc), but excludes non-renewable energies (natural gas and all fossil fuels).

Both concepts are based on a similar set of criteria, however some differences also exist between the two concepts.

CEC definition criteria (quotes from Electricity Dir., art. 2)	REC definition criteria (quotes from REDII, art.2)
“a legal entity”	“a legal entity”
“based on voluntary and open participation”	“based on open and voluntary participation”
-	“is autonomous”
“ is effectively controlled by members or shareholders”	“is effectively controlled by shareholders or members”
-	“shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the renewable energy projects”

“members or shareholders that are natural persons, local authorities, including municipalities, or small enterprises”	“shareholders or members of which are natural persons, SMEs or local authorities, including municipalities”
“its primary purpose to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits”	“primary purpose of which is to provide environmental, economic or social community benefits”

Table 1: Overview of CEC and REC main criteria according to their respective legal definitions

All the criteria detailed in the table above are functional criteria related to the way energy communities organise themselves. The type of activities they can perform remains quite open. Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) “may engage in generation, including from renewable sources, distribution, supply, consumption, aggregation, energy storage, energy efficiency services or charging services for electric vehicles or provide other energy services to its members or shareholders;” (Electricity Directive, Art. 2). Renewable Energy Communities (REC) are entitled to produce, consume, store and sell renewable energy; to perform energy sharing; and to access all suitable energy markets both directly or through aggregation Renewable Energy Directive (REDII), Art. 22). These two sets of activities hardly limit the activities of energy communities. The legislation keeps open to energy communities (renewable and citizen) the vast majority of traditional and innovative energy-related activities.

In parallel, there is no exclusivity between energy communities and any particular activity related to local energy management systems (e.g. closed distribution systems or micro-grids, or collective self-consumption). “The definition of citizen energy communities does not prevent the existence of other citizen initiatives such as those stemming from private law agreements.” (Electricity Directive, recital 44). Therefore, market actors who wish to implement collective self-consumption or microgrid can implement them using energy communities or traditional commercial arrangements. The diagram below illustrates legal concepts which can be used and put in place to implement innovative energy activities: (i) self-consumption performed by “prosumers” and which may be supported by a set of services (installation and maintenance; energy monitoring and self-consumption optimisation); (ii) “microgrids” including real-time balancing and the management of the distribution system in a given area. These two activities have been heavily debated at EU level and tend to be associated with CECs and RECs, whereas these notions are independent in the legislation. Self-consumption and collective self-consumption can be put in place by energy communities as they have the right to perform any energy services and access all markets, but it can also be performed by other, more conventional, market actors. The same applies for “microgrids”, which could be put in place through the implementation of a “Closed Distribution System (defined in the Electricity Directive, art. 38) or through a vertically integrated utility with less than 100.000 customers and therefore not subject to unbundling rules.

Figure 1: Different legal entities and legal activities options

Whatever the citizens ambition is to put in place these activities, energy communities do not hold in the EU legislation specific advantages to put in place innovative activities, nor do they represent a way to go through the unbundling requirements between system operation and the other energy provision activities.

Beyond innovative energy activities, the involvement of citizens can be beneficial to the energy system in various forms. For example, in the Netherlands citizens movements discuss the role energy communities can play in the planned phasing-out of gas and in the implementation of energy communities for district heating.

Recommendations

- The transposition of the Clean Energy Package should not limit energy communities to specific activities like collective self-consumption, but rather keep these open and insist on functional criteria.
- The transposition should also keep a strong coherence between RECs and CECs to keep a readable and consistent legislation for citizen initiatives.
- Member States should use the national assessment of potential and barriers for energy communities, requested in the REDII, to run a participatory process leading to a good understanding of existing citizen initiatives in order to build an appropriate enabling framework as required by this same directive.
- The REDII requires that Member States implement enabling frameworks for RECs and report about the concerned measures and their implementation in the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) (art. 22.4 and 22.5). Member States should include a monitoring of the number of existing RECs and report on their progression.
- In the context of the Dutch Climate Agreements (“klimaatakkoord”) concluded in 2019, the Dutch government set an indicative target of 50% of RES energy projects including citizen participation [3]. Other Member States should take similar measures to support the spread of energy communities.

2.2. Support energy communities in delivering demand-side energy services.

Citizen energy communities provide an alternative approach to conventional commercial offers. This way, they contribute on the local level to the global sustainability goals¹ and may provide an alternative approach to shortcomings of the market regarding the energy policy.

Energy communities are tailored tools to mobilise citizens around ethical concerns and sustainability goals. Many end-users of energy communities are driven by intrinsic motivations and are interested in social innovation. They engage into flexibility services more for social, sustainability and/or other ethical reasons such as contributing to the sustainable, green, global energy transition or improving quality of life in their neighbourhoods rather than for economic reasons. Cooperatives and CECs in general fulfil this value-oriented claim and provide citizens with a shared social and environmental goal rather than financial profit.

According to their legal definition, the energy communities are based on open participation and effectively controlled by their members (see table 1). They are tools of democratic revival aimed at involving citizens and allowing them to be represented and taken into account while decisions about their environment, community, houses are being taken.

Moreover, they are economic regenerative tools. A study showed that citizen energy projects may benefit two times more the local territory than private projects. Essentially due to local services hired and the redistributed revenues. This way, participants are building jointly owned projects in their community that will then be used for a wide range of energy and non-energy related actions, turning itself into a virtuous circle.

Figure 2: Citizen energy project benefits according to Energie Partagée [4]

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>, contribution of RECs to SDGs are namely: Number 7 (Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all), 11 (Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable), number 12 (Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns) and 13 (Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts)

In the context of demand-side flexibility services, an energy community may represent a trusted partner for a series of essential services:

- to handle their own consumer data and ensure their rights of data protection and data sovereignty
- to support the technical or administrative hustles of self-consumption or aggregation,
- to organise the service at collective level when such body is required (e.g. collective self-consumption at neighbourhood level).
- to hire needed commercial services to make the energy service function (including all range of energy services including ICT, from targeted software to all-in-one solutions).

In that sense, energy communities may act as complementary actors from organisations similar to co-ownership syndicates in the real-estate sector to more activist organisations committed to sustainability and self-sufficiency.

In the context of recovery plans being set-up in various EU Member States (e.g. call for projects in the context of the Spanish recovery plan [5]), the spread of innovative services like Demand-Side Flexibility (DSF) services among citizen- and renewable energy communities may be key to accelerate the energy transition and make it spread at residential level. Public authorities may set-up dedicated calls for projects in that direction.

Recommendations

- Taking into account the benefits of citizen initiatives, Member States should put in place “bike lanes” for RECs in renewables support schemes, adapted procedures for their specific nature;
- Member States should implement clear and simple regulatory frameworks for collective self-consumption and energy sharing on the local level.
- In the context of national recovery plans, policy-makers may set-up specific calls for projects for renewable energy communities setting up demand-side flexibility services.

3. PROMOTING RULES FIT FOR DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY IN THE DIFFERENT ENERGY MARKETS

Demand-side flexibility can be defined as the ability of an end-user to deviate from its normal electricity consumption (production) profile, in response to price signals or market incentives. Demand-side flexibility holds value all along the electricity system chain and the FLEXCoop consortium have identified the main service providers related to such services [6]. Some of these have been explored directly in FLEXCoop pilot sites, i.e. improved self-consumption, purchase of cheaper electricity on the wholesale market (Spanish pilot) and participation to TSO’s balancing reserves (Dutch pilot); some others may have been discussed in the different fora provided by the project.

The illustration below summarizes possible demand-side flexibility service providers, the related services they may offer and the beneficiaries.

Figure 3: Possible demand-side flexibility service providers, related services and beneficiaries

These different service providers will be the key actors of our emerging decentralised energy system. However, to make sure that their activities can develop, and the related services thrive for the benefit of the system some measures are still needed. The section below describes for each concerned market or mechanism, some key measures that could further support demand-side flexibility services.

3.1. Self-consumption: defining the right incentives

Net-metering schemes have represented simple and efficient incentives for self-consumption in the countries where it's been implemented. However, in the long run it provides the misleading signal that the whole grid can be used as a battery for free. Spain has put in place an interesting legislation in 2019 (RD 244/2019) [9], defining differentiated prices for retail electricity prices, and the “reward” for grid injection of energy surplus (which cannot exceed the energy cost amount in the monthly bill; the economic monthly balance cannot be negative).

By providing differentiated prices, the regulation offers an incentive to self-consume but also, as (i) the infamous “sun tax” on electricity produced and consumed in consumers premises was put to an end and (ii) retail prices remain higher than the “reward” for injection, it provides an incentive to consume as much from the self-produced electricity as possible. Indeed, this leads to a situation where (i) self-generated

electricity is cheaper than retail electricity (providing the incentive to self-generate) but (ii) electricity exported to the grid only offers a smaller value (providing the incentive to consume most of the self-generated electricity). These changes, incentivised by the Clean Energy Package, have known an early implementation in Spain where self-consumption is now returning to a situation of fast development.

Nevertheless, while the compensation price cannot exceed the price of electricity consumed from the public grid, this threshold on the “reward” put an economic limit to the size of self-consumption projects. The Art 21.2 (d) of the REDII [2] states “Member States shall ensure that renewables self-consumers, individually or through aggregators, are entitled: (...) (d) to receive remuneration, including, where applicable, through support schemes, for the self-generated renewable electricity that they feed into the grid, which reflects the market value of that electricity and which may take into account its long-term value to the grid, the environment and society.”. In order to maintain a minimum incentive to the installation of renewable project, a compensation should be maintained for each KWh injected to the grid. This may take the form of compensation based on wholesale market price coupled with a fix or floating a feed-in-premium.

Recommendations

- Public authorities should gradually move from net-metering schemes to alternatives valorising self-consumption optimisation and including differentiated price for retail electricity prices, electricity fed into the grid (or “reward”).
- Public authorities should reduce administrative burden and permit fast clearance for self-consumption facilities with low energy surplus.

- Avoid setting strong dis-incentive to maximised PV panels (beyond the concerned habitation needs), by providing some form of compensation for all kWh injected to the grid and by setting-up appropriate collective self-consumption (or energy sharing) rules (see recommendation 3.3, below).

3.2. Collective self-consumption (i): Providing a clear space of RECs and CECs

According to the Renewable Energy Directive, “Member States shall ensure that renewables self-consumers located in the same building, including multi-apartment blocks, are entitled to engage jointly in activities referred to in paragraph 2 [generate, store and sell their excess production of RES-E] and that they are permitted to arrange sharing of renewable energy that is produced on their site or sites between themselves” (Article 21(4)).

While the value citizen involvement and non-profit oriented approaches should be recognized all though the energy sector (see first recommendation in section 2.1 *Energy communities are not related to specific activities*), citizen and renewable energy communities may have a key role to play in developing collective self-consumption. This can allow for different business models to develop, and allow for choice by citizens.

Recommendations

- Member States should provide flexibility so that RECs and CECs have the option to engage in collective self-consumption (in a building or a condominium) and energy sharing (at neighbourhood level, using the local grid).
- Regardless of whether a legal entity is required or not, however, we recommend Member States ensure the possibility for citizens to engage in collective self-consumption through the establishment of a legal entity that qualifies as a REC or CEC.

3.3. Collective self-consumption (ii): Maximising roof-top PV panels installations through collective self-consumption

Through the new regulation introduced in Spain [9], the difference between retail price and surplus price (“reward”) on one side represent an incentive to self-consume more. However, on the other side, it also represents an economic limitation to the possible size of the PV panels to be installed. Indeed, even if the available surface is significant, the PV panels will be sized according to the consumption of the related building. Nevertheless, a smaller PV installation is a missed opportunity for RES generation and may still match consumers' needs in the immediate surroundings. For example, a second residence should be given the opportunity to join a collective self-consumption initiative, which would make beneficial the installation of full-size PV panels.

Renewable energy communities represent an opportunity to put in place citizens collectives consuming electricity from shared installations which can be major sizes. Collective-self consumption is a major opportunity to exploit the massive potential of exploiting distributed energy resources (DER) while limiting the investments needed in the local grid. However, these schemes as of today may be limited arbitrarily to a given perimeter. For example, in Spain the existing options are: sharing within a defined perimeter (500m), according to the set-up of the local grid (being fed by the same low-voltage cabin), or being located in the same cadastral reference (i.e. the same property which is useful for rural areas). These possible approaches should be well documented and information easily accessible. In particular regarding the set-up of the distribution grid, DSOs should then make publicly available the set-up of the local grid to make the implementation of collective self-consumption initiatives easy to plan and implement. Moreover, the limitation to 500 m hampers possibility to set-up collective self-consumption schemes at municipality-level. This is all the more damaging as municipalities are explicitly mentioned as possible members of energy communities and could lead collective self-consumption initiatives under this format.

Recommendations

- Public authorities should facilitate collective self-consumption with clear procedures and publicly available information.
- Member States should incentivize collective self-consumption by limiting grid fees when sharing energy by using the grid to the extent it has limited impact. In Spain, the regulation has recently changed from a “no fee” approach to a fee is “set as 0”, which may reduce the will to introduce higher costs in the future. This fee should be limited to a minimum, incentivising collective production and consumption and the multiplication of local installations.
- Enlarge the 500 m radius limitation for collective self-consumption to a higher distance which can stimulate municipality-level initiatives.
- DSOs should set-up clear rules and accompany the use of collective self-consumption as an opportunity for the implementation of distributed energy resources with limited impact on the grid.

3.4. Balancing reserves (i): Set-up market rules open to demand-side flexibility resources

Balancing mechanisms managed by European (Transmission Service Operators) TSOs represent a key path for the valorisation of DSF in the energy system. Because they valorise the capability to “react” closer to electricity delivery times, they are the schemes to best remunerate “flexibility”. However, the extensive regulatory framework analysis realised in the context of the FLEXCoop project [10] unveiled that aggregated loads cannot participate in many of these mechanisms throughout Europe, and remains rather constrained in those open markets where it may not be able to compete for services defined for standard generation sources.

Moreover, these schemes still have different requirements throughout Europe which represent a very fragmented market contrasting with the situation of the wholesale markets. This situation complicates the provision of trans-European solutions by aggregators and other service providers.

Finally, the use of demand response for grid congestion management is still at an early stage and as of today, the vast majority of EU network operators do not have the means to exploit this resource.

Recommendations

- All EU balancing mechanisms should open themselves to demand response resources.
- Balancing services requirements should be made “resource-agnostic” and minimum trading volumes should be reduced, to give room to a wider range of aggregated resources.
- The harmonisation of the different reserves mechanisms throughout Europe and related requirements (including the Imbalance Settlement Period (ISP)) should be pursued in order to enable pan-European solutions.
- The regular use of demand-side flexibility for grid management should be retributed (see recommendation 3.6 *Congestion management: include the possibility for prosumers to support the grid management in self-consumption schemes*)
- Standard demand response performance measurement and verification methods should be made available to provide an equal footing for service providers and facilitate service measurement in an accurate, transparent, simple and fair way.

3.5. Balancing reserves (ii): Improve requirements in aFRR procurement

The FLEXCoop project has stimulated the provision of automatic Frequency Restoration Reserves (aFRR) by a set of residential devices in the Dutch balancing mechanism. In the pilot site of Heeten, the control of residential heat pumps has been used to simulate aggregated resources of the Balancing Service Provider (BSP). In this demonstration, the FLEXCoop consortium has faced a set of difficulties.

- a) The Dutch Transmission Service Operator (TSO) requires the collection of metered data every 4 second for all participating units for settlement purposes. This is a very difficult requirement to meet when delivering balancing services with a large pool of aggregated DERs. Collecting and keeping such data for all grid connection points of small DERs makes residential devices aggregation difficult.
- b) Moreover, the minimum bid to participate into aFRR is 1MW. This threshold requires thousands of residential devices, which makes residential aggregators business cases difficult.
- c) Finally, aFRR in the Netherlands provides 2 options: (i) one-hour in advance free bidding or (ii) day-ahead contractual bids. The one-hour in advance free bidding is possible, however the day-ahead bidding is not a suitable scheme for most residential DER (e.g. with heat pumps used for heating and cooling buildings) if the service has to be committed for a whole day in advance, only limited flexibility can be guaranteed opposed to a scheme where only a few hours in advance are committed.

Recommendations

- Requirement of collecting “4 second data” for settlement may be implemented at aggregated level, through summarized measurements, e.g. within a given area or portfolio
- Requirement of minimum bids of 1 MW may be lowered to facilitate residential resources access.
- aFRR should take the limitations of forecasting flexibility of DERs into account and provide more suitable schemes with shorter commitment horizon.

3.6. Congestion management: include the possibility for prosumers to support the grid management in self-consumption schemes

Individual and, even more, collective self-consumption installations may create difficulties for the local network. These new projects may add new electricity flows where the network is not planned for it. DSOs, in that case, may not provide a connection authorisation until the network is reinforced

DSOs responsibility to ensure security of supply should not hamper the possibility for self-consumption initiatives where joint solutions exist. Demand-side flexibility solutions may be used to manage local grid congestion and avoid for example the overload of the grid at peak generation times. The entity initiating the self-consumption project may include demand-side

Individual and collective self-consumption may also support, in some specific cases, the DSO to manage and reduce grid congestions on a specific substation. In these cases, the added benefit to the system should be recognized and remunerated by the grid operator. The retribution of DSF services providers and aggregators would contribute to the valorisation of DSF services and expand the available solutions.

Recommendations

- When refusing connection authorisation to self-consumption initiatives for grid constraints reasons, DSOs should provide transparency on their decision and clarify the conditions that can be met through demand-side flexibility measures to authorise the project.
- In self-consumption schemes as any for other initiatives, the use of demand-side flexibility for grid management should be retributed to reflect the benefit to the grid (see recommendations. DSO may define a formula that takes into account the delayed or avoided investments in grid enhancement and extension).

3.7. Wholesale market: support the economics of flexibility for retailers offers

Retailers in today’s electricity market act as key mediator between individual consumers and electricity production made available on the market. Demand-side flexibility resources represent for them a key resource in the future to adapt to the challenges of increasing shares of renewable resources, varying with weather conditions (sun and wind).

DSF may enable them to “shape” their portfolio to better match the planned availability of cheap (and renewable) resources on the market or from their own portfolio, or help them to adapt real-time to ensure the balance of their portfolio.

Tax and levies, together with grid fees may represent more than two third of the retail prices, with great differences among EU Member States, as it is shown in the graph below.

Figure 4: Household prices in the EU in 2019 (DC band) according to Eurostat [7]

This limits the opportunity for retailers to provide dynamic pricing as the component of the retail price which changes is the energy component which may reflect wholesale prices volatility. However, an alternative to dynamic pricing consists in the supplier offering a

“bundled offer” where, by installing smart home controlling equipment, it can offer an overall cheaper retail offer to the consumer. However, this model hinders access for third-party aggregators.

Moreover, wholesale market prices should provide a clear signal for CO₂ emissions. The EU ETS until very recently have failed to provide such signals.

Figure 5: Price of CO₂ in the EU Emissions Trading System [8]

The latest reform (also known as “phase 4”) [27] may improve the situation, however in a context where the price on wholesale market is set by the cost of the marginal unit (“pay-as-clear”), renewable energy plants are unlikely to have a significant impact on prices until they reach a significant volume. Indeed, as wind and solar power units come with a minimal operational cost, the owners of such resources have most interest to bid at the lowest price to be selected anyhow. In this context, only an auction where all resources are RES would fully benefit from the low operational costs of these resources.

Recommendations

- Taxes and grid fees may hinder the signal provided by the wholesale market. Assess opportunities to set-up commercials using these price signals, using different business models.
- Support clear signals for CO₂-intensity at wholesale market level. Incentivise decarbonised generation through strong Emissions Trading System’s role, but also by anticipating the role or RES units on price formation.

3.8. Integrating flexibility valorisation opportunities

As of today, there are various emerging opportunities to valorise demand-side flexibility, though they may remain very limited in volume. An opportunity for DSF service providers to boost their activities and to expand more rapidly would be to see requests for flexibility from the different potential users streamlined and accessible in single marketplaces. These latter may take the form of local flexibility markets where requests from the TSO, the DSO together with the ones from Balance Responsibility Parties (BRPs) would be gathered in one place. Making them accessible in a single place through standardised format.

This implies an approach from the TSO and DSO regarding the aggregation of flexibility in the residential field so that cooperatives and the residential users could take complete advantage for the flexibility bidden in their domains.

Figure 6: The role of local flexibility market according to Regen [11]

Recommendations

- Research on the local flexibility market should be pursued (a representative sample of such initiatives have been gathered by the Florence School of Regulation in the context of the INTERRFACE project [12]).
- TSOs and DSOs should streamline their exchange of information in order to make compatible their request for flexibility and make possible the set-up of joint platforms which could take the role of local flexibility markets.

4. WIDENING DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY RESOURCES WITH THE APPROPRIATE RULES AND STANDARDS

Making demand-side flexibility resources available is a broad challenge, which consists in integrating a whole set of new resources into the energy system by means of communication technologies. With 20 dwellings involved and a broad set of devices (HVAC, lightning, EV and DHW) from different brands, the FLEXCoop consortium had a broad experience in connecting devices. The landscape of existing communication standards including protocols and semantic has been explored into details in FLEXCoop [13]. The general issue can be split into two challenges: (i) getting access to most buildings and (ii) involving as many relevant flexible appliances as possible. These appliances are diverse and may include consuming devices (“loads”), but also demand-side storage and generation.

Figure 7: Demand-side resources at building level

For a FLEXCoop solution to function all the links in the communication channel must be fully functional. This extends to the devices – in order to activate flexibility, it is necessary to reach the flexible appliances, however a series of obstacles still stand in the way.

4.1. At building level, promoting the Smart Readiness Indicator

Putting in place demand-side flexibility services, requires a whole communication and calculation infrastructure from the device to the service provider. This infrastructure encompasses:

- a real-time data collection system has to be installed including smart meters, clamps, sensors;
- they have to be compatible with and connected to the same communications system (additional in-house device like the FLEXCoop Open Smart Box or individual cloud connection per device).
- needed software include the relevant algorithms for the treatment of individual and aggregated data together with encryption and other security measures.

Therefore, the cost for accessing residential demand-side flexibility appears significant. Moreover, the available flexibility per load in the residential sector is very low, many loads have to be aggregated and the payback periods soar. For example, in the Dutch aFRR market, minimum bids of 1 MW are requested, which means in the domestic sector from 5,000 to 10,000 aggregated end users for a single bid.

Fortunately, the Article 8 of the new Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [14] introduced the SRI. This indicator mentioned already in the section above will consist in a rating “based on an assessment of the capabilities of a building or building unit to adapt its operation to the needs of the occupant and the grid and to improve its energy efficiency and overall performance” (Art. 8.10). The indicator itself is still work in progress and the object of a second technical support study by a consortium led by the Flemish Institute for Technological Research, VITO [15].

“The indicator is intended to raise awareness about the benefits of smart technologies and ICT in buildings (from an energy perspective, in particular), motivate consumers to accelerate investments in smart building technologies and support the uptake of technology innovation in the building sector. The indicator can also improve policy linkages between energy, buildings and other policy segments, in particular in the ICT area, and thereby contribute to the integration of the buildings sector into future energy systems and markets.”

VITO, Waide Strategic Efficiency, Ecofys and OFFIS [16]

Including buildings as interactive resources in the energy system would result in significant benefits for the energy system (an overview of this potential is available in [17]). The SRI initiative is key to reduce the costs associated with the installation and set-up of every participant in DSF schemes.

Recommendations

- The EU Commission should finalise the work on the creation of the Smart Readiness Indicator and make sure connectivity enabling demand-side flexibility services is being assessed along with the energy performance of the buildings.
- Regulators should pay special focus on the promotion of standards and initiatives such as the Smart Readiness Indicator in buildings, facilitating an early detection of smart dwellings where FLEXCoop big data platform can be easily deployed at a relatively low cost. At the same time, it would work towards smart equipment readiness in dwellings, to ensure a smooth and economically feasible data capturing infrastructure in buildings.

4.2. At device level, promote “Smart Grid Ready” interface among all brands of heat pumps

Heat pumps represent a promising technology to heat and cool houses in a decarbonised energy system. These thermal devices may also be flexible in the way they perform, without hampering the comfort of their users. Heat pumps flexibility was extensively examined in FLEXCoop and their diversity in communication protocols and controllability was indeed a challenge.

The German Heat Pumps Association (Bundesverband Wärmepumpe) has taken the initiative to promote the enhanced controllability of their members products.

The label defines four operating states for heat pumps which can be activated through external switching operations [18]. As a result, the power consumption can be increased or reduced for a limited time without going beyond safety limitations of the device. In 2017, 30 manufacturers and more than 1,000 heat pump models had this feature.

Beyond the interesting case of the SG ready label, controllability of heat pumps and of other residential devices remains limited. The SG ready label also only solves the technical interoperability issue to an extent.

- There is no prevailing communication standard for in-house devices and commonly found open interfaces are rather often badly documented.
- More importantly, the multiplication of “walled gardens” solutions proposed by devices vendors is problematic. It makes prosumers captive to the digital services offered by their device manufacturer.
- Moreover, there is a worrying trend in warranty contracts where clauses cancel the warranty-protection in case an open interface controls the device. These trends are clearly steps in the wrong direction with regards to actual interoperability.

There is a challenge in implementing a more uniform language and protocols landscape. A thorough review of related challenges is being proposed in FLEXCoop and Holisder joint paper on standardization [19] and in FLEXCoop deliverable D8.14 *FLEXCoop standardization punch-list and promotion activities - Final Version*.

Recommendations

- Market actors should encourage the spread of SG ready and similar initiatives for other devices.
- Market actors should monitor and encourage the emergence of common semantics and protocols for residential devices.
- Devices vendors should be encouraged to meet open data governance requirements.
- License agreements preventing the users to control their own appliances via open interfaces should be viewed negatively. Alternative should be found, without hampering the security of the concerned devices.

5. SUPPORTING STANDARDS AND TRUSTWORTHY ENERGY DATA

Demand-side flexibility services emerge from the opportunity created by new technology to manage our electricity system in real-time. In this context, the key resource to put in place demand-side flexibility services is data. This new dimension of energy services requires to define new rules and best practices to ensure data quality and the reliability of our energy system. Performance Measurement and Verification (PMV) have been the object of dedicated deliverables (D2.5 – *FLEXCoop PMV Methodology Specifications - Preliminary Version* and D2.8 – *Ibidem – Final Version*), whereas collective self-consumption has not been experimented directly in FLEXCoop, it represents a promising use case which stimulated reflection.

5.1. Creating standards for performance measurement and verification

Flexibility services, especially for balancing purposes, require the instant measurement of the up and down regulation provided in a given campaign by every participating unit. This measurement will determine the level of performance of the services and the associated remuneration. This measurement is based on complex mathematical models for short term energy forecasts both for consumption and generation, using consumption data fed by real time measurements from meters and sensors and comfort values to preserve the well-being of participating consumers.

However, each system actor may have different requirements for these calculations, especially TSOs defining balancing services provision requirements. Moreover, despite the key role they play in defining the quality of the service, PMV methodologies publicly available are scarce.

The lack of a PMV standard also diminishes the consumer confidence and the flexibility market actors since different methodologies and baseline models would conduct to different assessments of dispatched demand flexibility, thus undermining the usage of this valuable energy resource in the energy system.

On the other hand, data-driven systems in the domestic sector requires important investments in smart equipment, sensors, meters and communication data loggers. PMVs should be designed to forecast baselines per controllable load. The high costs of adapting heating, cooling, ventilation and hot water to be controllable may render FLEXCoop systems unfeasible from an economic point of view. Trends towards a smart readiness minimum level at home should be pushed forward, to enable automatically controlled solutions and artificial intelligence mechanisms for smart energy management in buildings (see recommendation 4.1 *At building level, promoting the Smart Readiness Indicator*).

Recommendation: Regulators and TSOs should create standards and guidelines for accepted and simplified PMV methodologies that reduce uncertainty and mistrust on complex and black-box technologies by the end-users.

5.2. Clarifying data gathering and data management in collective self-consumption schemes

Collective-self consumption (at building level) and energy sharing (peer-to-peer at neighbourhood level) are deemed promising activities for renewable energy communities and can be supported by digital tools like the FLEXCoop solution. However, a key support function is needed to make these innovative services possible. This is the management and certification of consumption and generation data. There are two main configurations for such a service to take place.

- 1- The service provider installs the smart metering equipment and is required to certify the energy produced and consumed between the energy producer and the energy consumers. In this case, a solution like FLEXCoop should incorporate a technology able to certify the energy transactions, such as blockchain.
- 2- The electricity generation and consumption data is provided by several electricity trader companies through the fiscal meters. In this case, the raw data measured by each company should be shared among the users involved. Besides, the entity responsible for certifying the transactions should not be able to alter the data and should be transparent in providing the measurements to each prosumer.

Recommendations

- Decision makers should clarify the procedures to certify the energy generated and consumed within collective self-consumption and energy sharing schemes
- Decision makers should include in the legislation specific recommendations related to security access and energy certification within collective self-consumption and energy sharing schemes.

6. IMPROVING DATA PRIVACY AND SECURITY IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

The emerging use of energy data and other consumer-related data in the energy sector triggers the important issue of data security and privacy. The General Data Protection Regulation issues a set of rules in this domain which are increasingly recognised international standards. However, some steps are needed to secure GDPR compliance in the energy sector. The FLEXCoop project took place when the GDPR was being implemented (the regulation was published in 2018 and implemented in 2018). Through the making of its Data Management Plan, including FLEXCoop data protection approach, the consortium had the opportunity to study and seek compliance with the GDPR.

6.1. Putting in place appropriate reporting on data protection for energy services

Despite the promotion of highly protective measures by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), good practices are missing for data protection measures in the energy sector. The available templates for Data Protection Impact Assessment is a “one-size-fits-all” methodology promoted by Expert Group 2 of the Smart Grid Task Force [20]. The requirement for the appointment of a Data Protection Officer in research projects is ambiguous. Overall, there is a missing link between the general requirements of the GDPR and the specific needs of innovative service in the energy sector. Expectations are unclear and dedicated entities in place (national data protection entities have much too limited resources) miss resources to fully ensure this role.

Recommendation: Decision-maker should publish modular templates and propose good practices for reporting energy services GDPR compliance.

6.2. Identifying authentication and pseudonymisation best practices

Data privacy and access to personnel data is a challenge to be addressed in any citizen-based collaborative scheme. The FLEXCoop consortium developed a security framework, based on combined OpenID-oAuth2 authentication and pseudonymization of private data which has demonstrated a high replicability potential. OAuth is an open standard for access delegation, commonly used as a way for Internet users to grant websites or applications access to their information on other websites but without giving them the passwords [30]. The OpenID standard allows for decentralized user authentication and the FLEXCoop system components utilize client service authentication. The claim feature of OpenID provides the base to grant fine granular access control rights through the use of different roles. Academia and market actors would highly benefit from exchanging best practices on this topic.

Recommendation: Decision makers, in particular the EU Commission, should define an appropriate forum to discuss authentication and other security best practices for energy services.

7. DATA SOVEREIGNTY: IMPLEMENT STRONG DATA GOVERNANCE STRATEGIES AND JOIN THE EUROPEAN ENERGY DATA SPACE INITIATIVE.

Beyond the necessity to protect citizens as data subjects, the digital economy creates opportunity for civil society to act in favour of a more democratic society. This may occur through anticipated strategies on the re-use of data but also by the promotion of EU initiatives maintaining sovereignty on the data infrastructure. The FLEXCoop project has been the opportunity for cooperatives to experiment digital energy services. The recommendations below are meant to help them to map the next steps to secure their citizen approach in this growing sector.

7.1. Putting in place “energy data strategy” for energy cooperatives

In the energy sector, the competition on digitalised energy services is increasing and with it the attempts to access or retain consumer data. From home automation solution offered by digital majors (e.g. “Google Home” or Amazon “Alexa”), to devices manufacturers own platforms (like the platform “Wibutler” presented by the heat pump manufacturer Viessmann as supporting the uniform control of smart home technology [22]), initiatives in this domain are flourishing. However, the leading energy platforms, services and assets are mostly closed-source, proprietary and centralized. They create content “silos” causing vendor lock-in, hindering market participation of the local level (prosumers), limiting prosumer choices and making it difficult for prosumers to control, exploit and profit from their own data “property”. These silos and closed proprietary platform hinders the capability for individuals to benefit from multi-devices services and hampers the capability for energy communities to offer meaningful aggregated services (energy monitoring, energy efficiency, and demand-side flexibility services)

In the data economy cooperatives and other citizen energy communities should be able to control their data and decide at a granular level what is done with them and whether they can re-use their energy data for different purposes. For example, the expanding domain of “predictive maintenance” could represent interesting data use and benefits for citizens. “Predictive maintenance” consists in using all data generated during the life cycle of a given asset for its own maintenance or for broader studies. In the energy sector, the data analysis of the “local data” promises turbine manufacturers, turbine operators or distribution system operators (DSO) significant savings on their operational costs.

In order to invest in such new areas, citizens may create dedicated entities and there are already initiatives to give individuals the tools and means to decide at a collective level what is done with their data (e.g. “mydata” movement [23]). The European Commission recently introduced the term and the set-up of so called “data cooperatives” in its proposal for the European Data Governance Act [24] in this context.

“Data cooperatives seek to strengthen the position of individuals in making informed choices consenting to data use, influencing the terms and conditions of data user organisations attached to data use or potentially solving disputes between members of a group on how data can be used when such data pertain to several data subjects within that group.”

European Commission [24], p.18

As the digital economy is expanding, citizen initiatives in the energy sector would benefit from protecting their rights as data subjects but decide what can be done with their data should it be for as a service (e.g. predictive maintenance) or for societal purposes.

Recommendations:

- Cooperatives should seek for a strong governance framework for their own data access and usage. They should strengthen their governance mechanisms for data usage of data that they themselves have produced with the other stakeholders of the value chain. Cooperatives should work out and follow a clear “energy data strategy” anticipating economic opportunities and possible societal benefits of border data availability.
- Cooperatives could possibly seek to extend their focus into becoming also “data cooperatives”. This can be done in line with the principles on Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) of data taking into account the developments and decisions of sector-specific authorities.
- In addition to clear rules on the rights to use the data, industry-wide agreements on the use of standards and data formats are also required. Agreements are needed so that new application developments do not have to be individually adapted to individual companies, but can be used throughout the process.
- Energy cooperatives should be supported in enforcing their rights with regard to the use of the data they generate and to strengthen the democratization aspect of their activity from this dimension.

7.2. Making use of public infrastructure to maintain sovereignty on strategic assets

Digital energy services require the availability and cross sector sharing of energy data, in a secure and trustworthy manner to facilitate innovative solutions. In this context, the European Commission supports the set-up of so called “Energy Spaces” enabling the use and reuse of energy data in their recent European Data Strategy [28].

Increasingly, these last years, the European Commission has been focusing on enabling new digital business models for individuals and SMEs. Supporting a networked economy with complimentary and cooperating actors, but also transparent algorithms and interoperable data. These principles are at the forefront of the European cloud service GAIA-X [29]. This joint initiative by Germany and France aims to create an open, secure and trustworthy European platform for small and medium-sized cloud providers via a common standard. The aims are twofold: (i) to offer an alternative to large stakeholders and uphold European data protection standards, and (ii) to create a European data innovation ecosystem to promote competitiveness for individual small providers.

At centre of the GAIA-X data-infrastructure is the concept of domain specific “data spaces”. The International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), a founding member of the GAIA-X has extended this general concept of data spaces by proposing a reference architectural model to ensure “digital sovereignty” and trust among its participants. According to IDSA, digital sovereignty is “the ability of a natural or legal person to exclusively and sovereignly decide concerning the usage of data as an economic asset.” [25]

The IDSA’s approach is interesting to the extent it does not provide a data lake or a cloud, but rather a peer-to-peer network. Only the participants can exchange data bilaterally and there is no central authority that can be corrupted. Moreover, the connectors include a number of security mechanisms, in particular the use of the container technology. The data are in a different container than the applications, i.e. they cannot corrupt each other. Finally, identity management also has its own approach. Each connector and user require their own digital identity certificate to guarantee that it really is the appropriate component and company.

The IDSA is aiming at offering energy data spaces with three objectives: (i) interoperability with a wide variety of data, (ii) trusted data/ data models sharing with governance and (iii) security between multiple data sources (owners, producers, users, consumers) along the value chain. Several companies are already cooperating towards such a data space and invite all European companies, organisations, suppliers and producers, working and producing data within the energy sector to join.

Recommendations

- As a strategic step, cooperatives should consider to work together, dock at and use the new European interoperable cloud infrastructures that the EC will be providing and participate in the common European “energy data space” designed for European SMEs as described in the European data strategy rather than develop or commission energy own IT-infrastructure for themselves.

- The availability and cross-sector sharing of energy data in a secure and trustworthy in the European energy data space can facilitate the development of cooperative energy data related business cases for cooperatives.

8. IMPROVING RESEARCH CONDITIONS IN THE DEMAND-SIDE FLEXIBILITY SERVICES SECTOR

Demand-side flexibility and other digitalised energy services have passed the stage of early infancy, but will require research and innovation in the years to come. In this context, some key measures may improve and accelerate the development of new energy services. FLEXCoop had the opportunity to benefit from some research support initiatives, at EU level through its participation to INEA clustering activities, but also at national level, thanks to the favourable environment provided to its pilot in the Netherlands.

8.1. Improving classification of the different modelling approaches regarding demand-side flexibility

When taking part into INEA clustering activities², FLEXCoop partners faced some limitations to exchange on modelling. As of today, there is no sound classification of the different modelling approaches regarding demand-side flexibility. This situation hampers cooperation among research projects and makes difficult comparison and exchange of experience. Such categories may distinguish the following aspects:

- (i) Operational:
 - Predictive: using weather and calendar information (and other forecasts) as input
 - Decision-making: optimizing in some real-time setting: (Milliseconds (frequency control); Hours (e.g. day-ahead planning, price response); Months (e.g. fuel purchase))
 - Modelling approach is mainly data-driven, i.e. real-time data from systems such that online decision making is possible.
- (ii) Planning:
 - Predictive: Long-term, run through long period
 - Decision-making: what happens in different scenarios
 - Modelling approach is mainly “physics” driven, i.e. the systems are characterised with their properties and it's simulated what will happen in different scenarios.
 - Should include “operational” optimization!

Recommendation: Research cooperation activities should include the categorization of different types of modelling, making possible to get an overview of what type of modelling is applied and available in projects and stimulating exchange of experience among the research community. This could take place in Bridge or similar collaboration groups.

² H2020 Low TRL Smart Grids and Storage Projects clustering events and working group

8.2. Making accessible for researchers and start-uppers broader sets of information related to close-to-market DSF services

The Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [21] has explored the different use of demand-side flexibility services, their requirements and business opportunities. This work represents a precious standardisation effort for researchers and start-uppers. Moreover, the knowledge exchange initiatives in the field of smart grids led by the Commission, namely BRIDGE³ and INEA clustering activities, represent valuable opportunities to exchange among peers. In this context, BRIDGE and similar activities or USEF itself could dedicate part of their activities to completing the USEF framework with documented close-to-market examples in order to stimulate replication and improvement.

Recommendation: Complete the USEF framework with documented examples on implemented services in close-to-market conditions.

8.3. Promoting the setup of regulatory sandboxes

A whole wave of new digital energy services is coming out of the research and innovation activities of the past years and the usefulness of regulatory sandboxes in the energy sector is being discussed in the EU. A regulatory sandbox can be defined as a closed environment, based on agreed rules with the regulator, granting some exceptions in order to run experimental activities in close-to-real life conditions. The Florence School of Regulation provides a clear description of their purpose [26]: “The motivation behind setting up a regulatory sandbox is two-fold. First, allow innovators to test new technologies and business models that are only partially compatible with the existing legal and regulatory framework. Second, allow regulators to learn about particular innovations. As such, regulators can develop the right regulatory environment to accommodate them.”.

The FLEXCoop project has benefited from the situation of the cooperative Endona who is performing several experiments through the regulatory sandbox provided by the regulator around the area of Heeten. This situation enabled FLEXCoop to benefit from the dynamic set-up of a citizen cooperative, itself involved into broader responsibilities and having direct link with system actors (DSO and TSO). Situation created an environment rich in interactions which directly benefited the project.

Recommendation: Regulatory sandboxes, like the one provided by the Dutch authorities in Heeten where market actors can experiment new services are very beneficial for the development of new solutions, and should be multiplied.

³ European Commission’s knowledge exchange initiative gathering Horizon 2020 projects related to Smart Grid, Energy Storage, Islands and Digitalisation Projects. More info at: www.h2020-bridge.eu

9. CONCLUSION

Energy cooperatives, representing the vast majority of existing energy communities, have historically focused their activities on energy production. The emergence of new technologies and new possible services open a new era for citizen initiatives who may become key actors in the decentralisation of our energy system. Many factors will contribute to the success of such process, and among them it is key that decision makers and market actors acknowledge the role of citizens initiatives, and of the possible contribution of the demand-side to a secure and decarbonised energy system. The multiplication of energy communities taking an active role in the management of distributed energy resources may be a key to ensure the resilience of our energy system.

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